

METHODOLOGICAL INTERPRETATIONS IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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There is also a discussion of foreign language teaching methods and the types of modern approaches used in them and their benefits. If teachers or scientists do not choose an appropriate method for learning and teaching, the expected results will not be achieved. Scientific learning methods cover each stage of language learning and analyze their practical significance.

This article is devoted to each aspect of the topic and the description of new, modern innovative methods that are important to use. It helps to increase the range of skills on learning and teaching and to achieve great success on language studying.

Teaching foreign languages and learning some aspects of particular language are a bit challenging on the other hand it is a rewarding job. Most scientists spend their time on

ABSTRACT

This article discusses about useful, non-traditional methods and techniques of language learning and their practical significance. In addition, a description of each method and techniques is provided for learning and teaching some significant aspects of languages. The main purpose of using such kind methods in the field of language learning is to arise students' interest in language skills, to increase their knowledge of the language and use of important aspects of language

learning some useful branches or aspects of the language. Now with the help of technological devices learning foreign languages is very easy and they help to save time.

These devices are very beneficial for teachers to teach their pupils perfectly. There are some methods of teaching languages:

1. Understanding through grammatical rules.

Grammar is one of the most popular language teaching methods which has been used

as an effective way from the past to present.

This way is based on theoretical knowledge and some rules. In this way pupils can learn only rules and grammatical structure of sentences and then they can analyze texts

according to grammatical knowledge and outlook. Besides that they can make some

examples about the given rules. Now This method is used widely in modern schools of

developed countries, such as in England, the USA.

2. Translation.

Translation is the main communication of a source-language. This approach is based on vocabulary and their meaning. If pupils translate some sentences or text, their vocabulary will enhance and then they will have an ability to do any task without difficulties according to translate the words truly. For instance, this method mostly helps for scientists to know the meaning of research and some scientific works. This approach is also beneficial. The role of interpreters is absolutely great to develop this method because they are the main people who work on the field of specialization.

3. Audio-lingual method.

This method grew indirectly out of a program developed by American linguists and psychologists for the US Army during the Second World War. But it really took shape when American Structural Linguistics and Behaviorist Psychology were adopted as the twin foundations of a 'scientific' approach of foreign language teaching in the late 1950s. It is similar in many ways to Situational Language Teaching, but there are some notable differences. This is one of the famous methods which is used in teaching foreign languages. Sometimes it is called Army Method, or New Key. The main great feature of this method is that the examples of behaviorism can be seen as an important theory. Some aspects of this method looks like the Direct Method. This method teaches pupils and students to use foreign

languages and their possibilities, such as new words and grammar of it than their native language. Because the possibilities of their own language are no so wide and new for them but learning some aspects of foreign language helps people to get new information and enrich the worldview. The main of this method is teaching grammar and its rules. Unlike some of other methods, it does not prefer using and teaching vocabulary.

In Audio-lingual Method there are two main activities which are named dialogue repetition and memorization, and substitution drilling. The dialogues are pronounced in a new structure or contextualized models, people should remember and write some significant points of it. The substitution drilling is very extensive and intensive, it has a great structure which is often uncontextualized.

4. Communicative language teaching (CLT) or Communicative approach (CA).

This is a type of approach which is mostly related to the speech of people. This approach learns and practices interactions related to language and their purposes, the use of languages both at lessons and outside of class.

Learners share their ideas about personal experiences with their partners and they exchange their language skills with each other. That method is also used to encourage speakers to express their experiences into the environment of language learning. CLT has some benefits which help not only students or pupils but also teachers to use during lessons. Because oration plays a key role to make lessons more effective and interesting

5. Direct Method.

This method aims at learning through listening and speaking. It does not learn about grammar. As it does not focus on the rules, it does not matter making some mistakes because they are minor faults. There is not any limitation for using this method. Oral communication is the main object because the direct approach uses speaking more than reading and writing skills. This method encourages pupils or students to express their thoughts in spite of having some grammatical mistakes.

6.Total Physical Response(TPR).

Total Physical Response (TPR) as a not exclusive but certainly central method in in

foreign language teaching proves to be an excellent solution in speeding up learning as linguistic output is acquired through the use of the kinesthetic system associated with the sense of sight, hearing and touch (multisensory learning).

In this approach visual cues have great importance. Pupils or students need to see image or the action of the theme many times so as to learn new words and other aspects of language on this topic. With the help of this method people can develop their listening

skills. During practicing with this method they should pay attention to new words and mainfacts. It gives people some opportunities to communicate using newly acquired words.

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